

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A study of κ - Contraction and the Triangular α Orbital Admissibility Condition in Quasi-metric Space

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Abstract

Objective: To establish the presence of fixed point under a novel contraction condition and a freshly defined distance function, we harness the concept of triangular α orbital admissible mappings. **Method:** Consider two mapping in quasi-metric space. These two mapping satisfy a new contraction condition and also the triangular α orbital admissible condition. Define the sequences for two mappings. Consider two cases for odd and even sequences. Show that a fixed point is common for two mappings and then demonstrate its uniqueness. **Findings:** Unique common fixed point exists. **Novelty:** A new technique is used, so the length of proof become very short as compare to theorems available in literature.

Keywords: Quasi metric; Fixed point; α Orbital admissible; Function; κ Contraction

1 Introduction

The foundational principle of Banach Contraction, known for its precision and efficacy, forms the bedrock of metric fixed point theory. It offers a systematic approach for addressing a wide array of problems across mathematical sciences, economics and engineering. Numerous authors have explored applications, extensions and advancements of this principle in diverse directions. In various spaces such as b-metric space, Cone metric space, Menger space, Fuzzy metric space, G-metric space, Quasi metric space, researchers have established fixed point theorems.

Our focus lies on quasi-metric spaces, chosen due to their fewer constraints compared to metric spaces, leading to distinct results. Recent work of authors⁽¹⁾ and⁽²⁾ have delved into quasi- metric spaces. The term “generalized contraction” was introduced by⁽³⁾, while⁽⁴⁾ presented the concept of “almost z-contraction” within metric spaces. In dislocated quasi-metric space,⁽⁵⁾ has demonstrated a fixed point theorem for Geraghty quasi-contraction type mappings, employing classical methods for proof.⁽⁶⁾ concentrated on quasi-partial b-metric space and established non-unique fixed points.⁽⁷⁾ employed the concept of quasi-triangular orbital admissible mapping in a complete metric space, whereas we applied this concept in context of quasi-metric spaces.

The proposed study is distinguished from these findings because we need not require to prove Cauchy sequence as we have added a concept of triangular α orbital admissible “ κ -distance function”, along with a unique contraction condition and a novel technique for proving the existences of a unique fixed point. Furthermore, our approach reduces the length of the proof for the theorem, enhancing the efficiency of method outlined in this paper.

Definition (8): The mapping $q : I \times I \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ termed as Quasi Metric, if it fulfills:

- (i) $q(i, j) = 0 \Leftrightarrow i = j$
- (ii) $q(i, j) \leq q(i, l) + q(l, j), \forall i, j, l \in I$

The couple (I, q) termed as quasi-metric space.

Definition (9): Consider a non- empty set I and a function $\alpha : I \times I \rightarrow [0, \infty)$. Then the mapping $F : I \rightarrow I$ is triangular α orbital admissible, if it is α orbital admissible plus.

$$\alpha(i, j) \geq 1 \text{ and } \alpha(j, Fj) \geq 1 \Rightarrow \alpha(i, Fj) \geq 1$$

Remark 1: In this context, it’s important to note that a metric space encompasses quasi-metric space as a subset, but opposite relationship does not always hold.

Remark 2: The conclusions that hold true in quasi-metric space do not necessarily hold true in metric space.

Example: Let $I = (0, \infty)$ Define $q(i, j) = \begin{cases} j, i \geq j \\ \frac{j-i}{4}, i < j \end{cases}$

Here, we observe $q(i, j) \neq q(j, i)$, indeed it pertains the quasi-metric space rather than a metric space.

The objective of the current study is to define a new function, new contraction condition and also apply fixed point theory to quasi-metric space.

2 Result and Discussion

We have defined κ - function as here under:

Definition: A function $\kappa : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is named as κ -distance function when κ satisfies $\kappa(x^*) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x^* = 0$

Now, using new contraction condition, definition of κ -distance function and utilizing the concept of triangular α orbital admissible, we prove the theorem, as stated below:

Theorem 2.1: Assume (I, q) metric space, $F : I \rightarrow I, G : I \rightarrow I$ be triangular α orbital admissible mappings. The pair (F, G) fulfilling the succeeding contraction for each $i, j \in I$.

- (i) $\alpha(i, j) \kappa(q(Gi, Fj)) \leq \kappa \{a_1 q(i, j) + a_2 q(i, Gi) + a_3 q(j, Fj) + a_4 q(i, Fj) + a_5 q(Gi, j)\}$
- (ii) $\alpha(i, j) \kappa(q(Fi, Gj)) \leq \kappa \{a_1 q(i, j) + a_2 q(i, Fi) + a_3 q(j, Gj) + a_4 q(i, Gj) + a_5 q(Fi, j)\}$

Also assume $q(i_n, i_{n+1}) = 0$ or $q(i_{n+1}, i_n) = 0$, for some $n \in NU\{0\}, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i \leq 1$. Then i_n is unique common fp of F, G .

Proof: Consider $i_0 \in I$, the sequence $\{i_n\}$ in I be defined by

$$F(i_{2n}) = i_{2n+1} \text{ and } G(i_{2n+1}) = i_{2n+2} \text{ for all } n \in NU\{0\}. \quad (2.1.1)$$

Consider the following cases

Case 1: $q(i_n, i_{n+1}) = 0$. If n is even, the $n = 2k$ for some $k \in NU\{0\}$. $\therefore q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) = 0$ (2.1.2)

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2})) &\leq \alpha(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) \kappa\{q(Gi_{2k}, Fi_{2k+1})\} \leq \kappa\{a_1 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) + \\ &a_2 q(i_{2k}, Gi_{2k}) + a_3 q(i_{2k+1}, Fi_{2k+1}) + a_4 q(i_{2k}, Fi_{2k+1}) + a_5 q(Gi_{2k}, i_{2k+1})\} \\ &= \kappa\{a_1 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) + a_2 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) + a_3 q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) + a_4 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+2}) + \\ &a_5 q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+1})\}, \text{ using (2.1.1)} \\ &= \kappa\{(a_3 + a_4) q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2})\}, \text{ using (2.1.2)} \\ &\therefore q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1})) &\leq \alpha(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k}) \kappa\{q(Fi_{2k+1}, Gi_{2k})\} \\ &\leq \kappa\{a_1 q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k}) + a_2 q(i_{2k+1}, Fi_{2k+1}) + a_3 q(i_{2k}, Gi_{2k}) + a_4 q(i_{2k+1}, Gi_{2k}) \\ &\quad + a_5 q(i_{2k}, Fi_{2k+1})\} \\ &= \kappa\{a_1 q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k}) + a_2 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+2}) + a_3 q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) + a_4 q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+1}) \\ &\quad + a_5 q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k})\} \\ &= \kappa\{(a_2 + a_5) q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1})\} \\ &\text{using (2.1.2) and (ii) of definition (8)} \\ &\therefore q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) = 0 \\ &\therefore q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) = 0 = q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) = 0 = q(i_{2k}, i_{2k+1}) \Rightarrow i_{2k} = i_{2k+1} = i_{2k+2}$, by (i) definition ⁽⁸⁾
 $\Rightarrow i_n = i_{n+1} = i_{n+2} \Rightarrow i_n = Gi_n = Fi_{n+1}$

Hence i_n is common fixed point of F and G for even value of n .

Case 2: $q(i_n, i_{n+1}) = 0$. If n is odd, then $n = 2k + 1$ for some $k \in NU\{0\}$

$\therefore q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) = 0$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+3})) &\leq \alpha(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) \kappa\{q(Fi_{2k+1}, Gi_{2k+2})\} \\ &\leq \kappa\{a_1q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) + a_2q(Fi_{2k+1}, i_{2k+1}) + a_3q(i_{2k+2}, Gi_{2k+2}) + a_4q(i_{2k+1}, Gi_{2k+2}) \\ &\quad + a_5q(i_{2k+2}, Fi_{2k+1})\} \\ &= \kappa\{a_1q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k}) + a_2q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) + a_3q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+3}) + a_4q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+3}) \\ &\quad + a_5q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+2})\} \\ &= \kappa\{(a_3 + a_4)q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+3})\} \\ &\therefore q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+3}) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(q(i_{2k+3}, i_{2k+2})) &\leq \alpha(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) \kappa\{q(Gi_{2k+2}, Fi_{2k+1})\} \\ &\leq \kappa\{a_1q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) + a_2q(i_{2k+2}, Gi_{2k+2}) + a_3q(i_{2k+1}, Fi_{2k+1}) + a_4q(i_{2k+2}, Fi_{2k+1}) \\ &\quad + a_5q(Gi_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1})\} \\ &= \kappa\{a_1q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) + a_2q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+3}) + a_3q(i_{2k+1}, i_{2k+2}) + a_4q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+2}) \\ &\quad + a_5q(i_{2k+3}, i_{2k+1})\} \\ &= \kappa\{a_5q(i_{2k+3}, i_{2k+2})\} \\ &\therefore q(i_{2k+3}, i_{2k+2}) = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow q(i_{2k+3}, i_{2k+2}) = 0 = q(i_{2k+2}, i_{2k+1}) \Rightarrow i_{2k+1} = i_{2k+2} = i_{2k+3} \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow i_n = i_{n+1} = i_{n+2} \Rightarrow i_n = Gi_n = Fi_{n+1}$.

Hence i_n is common fixed point of F and G for odd value of n .

3 Uniqueness of fixed point

$\kappa(q(p_1, p_2)) = \kappa\{q(Gp_1, Fp_2)\}$, where p_1 and p_2 are distinct fixed points.

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \kappa\{a_1q(p_1, p_2) + a_2q(p_1, Gp_2) + a_3q(p_2, Fp_2) + a_4q(p_1, Fp_1) + a_5q(Gp_1, p_2)\} \\ &= \kappa\{(a_1 + a_2 + a_5)q(p_1, p_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

$\therefore q(p_1, p_2) = 0 \Rightarrow p_1 = p_2$

F and G therefore share a single fixed point.

Example: Let $I = R, q : I \times I \rightarrow (0, \infty), \alpha : I \times I \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ defined by

$$\alpha(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } i, j \geq 0, i \geq j \\ \frac{1}{20}, & \text{for } i, j < 0, i \geq j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, q(i, j) = 2(i - j)$$

$$k(x^*) = \frac{x^*}{1 + \frac{x^*}{2}}$$

$F : I \rightarrow I$, defined by $F(i) = \frac{i}{1+2i}$ and $G : I \rightarrow I$ defined by $G(i) = \frac{i}{8}$.

Let $a_1 = 0.2, a_2 = 0.3, a_3 = 0.1, a_4 = 0.1, a_5 = 0.2 \therefore \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i = 0.9 < 1$.

Case 1: $i, j \geq 0, i \geq j$. Consider $i = 2, j = 1$. Then in condition (i) of theorem 2.1

L.H.S. = -0.1818 and R.H.S. = 0.89.

Then in condition (ii) of theorem 2.1

L.H.S. = 0.43 and R.H.S. = 0.89

Case 2: $i, j \geq 0, i \geq j$. Consier $i = -1, j = -2$. Then in condition (i) of theorem 2.1

L.H.S. = -1.0246 and R.H.S. = 0.9333

Then in condition (ii) of theorem 2.1

L.H.S. = 0.055 R.H.S. = 0.0952.

Therefore all conditions specified in theorem 2.1 are met and $F(0) = G(0) = 0$. Therefore 0 is unique common fixed point for both F and G .

4 Conclusion

A new function and a new condition in quasi metric space has given singular common fixed point statement. The idea of triangular α orbital admissible function is useful to prove the result in very few steps. The theorem can be extended for four mappings.

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References

- 1) Qawasmeh T, Tallafha A, Shatanawi W. Fixed and common fixed point theorems through modified w distance mappings. *Nonlinear Functional Analysis and Applications*. 2019;24(2):221–239. Available from: <https://web.archive.org/web/20200723045629/http://nfaa.kyungnam.ac.kr/journal-nfaa/index.php/NFAA/article/viewFile/1168/1005>.
- 2) Shoaib A, Arshad M, Rasham T. Some Fixed point results in ordered complete dislocated quasi Gd metric space. *Journal of Computational analysis and applications*. 2021;29(6). Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336650444_Some_fixed_point_results_in_ordered_complete_dislocated_quasi_Gd_metric_space.
- 3) Hossain A, Khan FA, Khan QH. A Relation-Theoretic Metrical Fixed Point Theorem for Rational Type Contraction Mapping with an Application. *Axioms*. 2021;10(4):316. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms10040316>.
- 4) Karapınar E, Bindu VMLH. Discussions on the almost \mathbb{E} -contraction. *Open Mathematics*. 2020;18(1):448–457. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1515/math-2020-0174>.
- 5) Umudu JC, Olaleru JO, Mogbademu AA. Fixed point results for Geraghty quasi-contraction type mappings in dislocated quasi-metric spaces. *Fixed Point Theory and Applications*. 2020;2020(1):16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13663-020-00683-z>.
- 6) Gautam P, Singh SR, Kumar S, Verma S. On Nonunique Fixed Point Theorems via Interpolative Chatterjea Type Suzuki Contraction in Quasi-Partial b-Metric Space. *Journal of Mathematics*. 2022;2022:1–10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/2347294>.
- 7) Rakesh T, Shashi T. Common Fixed Point Theorem for Pair of Quasi Triangular α -Orbital Admissible Mappings in Complete Metric Space with Application”. *Malaya Journal of Matematik*. 2023;11(02):167–80. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.26637/mjm1102/006>.
- 8) W W. On quasi-metric spaces. *American Journal of Mathematics*. 1931;53:675–684. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2371174>.
- 9) Popescu O. Some new fixed point theorems for α -Geraghty contraction type maps in metric spaces. *Fixed Point Theory and Applications*. 2014;2014(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1687-1812-2014-190>.